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A CONCEPTUAL MODEL FOR SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL PROGRAMS RESULTS DISSEMINATION EFFICIENCY ANALYSIS

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Annotation: The analysis of the problems of identification of actors and restructuring of the initial data sets in the process of dissemination of the results of scientific and technological programs is carried out. It is proposed to analyze the dissemination of STP results based on models in which the individual states of actors are defined as susceptibility, interest, awareness and antagonism. A conceptual model of differential dynamics has been developed for analyzing the STP results dissemination effectiveness in scientific cooperation networks, which includes latency and feedback mechanisms, which are more consistent with the STP results dissemination process nature.

Keywords: actor, conceptual model, system analysis, scientific collaboration, scientific and technical program

For a long time, bibliography has been a classical form of storing data on scientific activity in one or several fields [1, 2]. Bibliographic records contain important summary information about scientific activity, dissemination of knowledge by research organizations. From this point of view, the bibliographic record reveals two different but interrelated sets of relationships: the social relationship between researchers; a cognitive structure that reveals the relationships established by researchers.

In science and technology dissemination activities, the two sets of relationships correspond to two different but interrelated networks (scientific collaboration networks and knowledge dissemination networks). In a collaborator network, which in the narrow sense is a kind of scientific collaboration network, the two networks can be described.

The scientific collaboration network is a network formed by the joint participation of research organizations for scientific and technical programs (STP). Its evaluate represents the number of times that two different scientists appear in the same article (the scientific collaboration between researchers' frequency) [3, 4].

A knowledge dissemination network is a network formed by the co-emergence of researchers and knowledge. Its measure is the knowledge amount that the researcher owns, which reflects the knowledge distribution (the researchers' cognitive state) [5, 6].

The construction of two networks is the basis for the analysis and study of the scientific and technical program knowledge essence disseminated in the network through scientific cooperation. In empirical analysis, actors are the research object. If an actor publishes the results of his research containing certain STP knowledge, this means that the actor has mastered the knowledge and can disseminate it among others.

The scientific and technical programs new knowledge dissemination based on scientific cooperation, should be considered as a process in which knowledge penetrates or spreads from the initial actors of a specific program to the implementation of knowledge synergy, intersection, integration, development and innovation by actors of the national innovation system.

It is proposed to analyze the dissemination of STP results based on models in which the individual states of the actors are defined as the susceptibility state, the interest state and the carrier state, as well as the antagonistic state. They can pass from one state to another with a certain probability. However, in the course of the dissemination of knowledge within the scientific cooperation framework, two special phenomena are observed: when receiving certain knowledge, the actor seeks not to disseminate knowledge immediately. Instead, there is a certain period of time during which he assimilates knowledge [7, 8]. After the actor assimilates and transforms knowledge into internal knowledge, he will spread this knowledge among other actors. Under the influence of internal factors (such as changes in research direction and interests) and external factors (such as socio-economic and political), the actor may no longer disseminate knowledge. However, this kind of behavior is temporary because actors will again accept and disseminate knowledge in the future. Thus, a model is proposed that has a certain latency state and a feedback mechanism that are more consistent with the knowledge dissemination process nature in the scientific and technological program framework and are more suitable for functioning as a basic differential dynamics model for the knowledge dissemination in scientific cooperation networks.

In order to formalize the knowledge exchange and dissemination process in detail, it is proposed to divide actors at different knowledge dissemination stages in scientific cooperation networks into four categories (see Figure): potential

knowledge recipients; potential disseminate knowledge actors; knowledge disseminators; non-disseminating actors.

1. Potential STP knowledge recipients: actors who have not yet acquired knowledge.
2. Potential actors disseminating STP knowledge: actors who have acquired knowledge, but have not yet disseminated it.
3. Actors disseminating STP knowledge: actors who have acquired knowledge and disseminate it among potential knowledge recipients.
4. Actors non-disseminating STP knowledge: actors who have acquired knowledge, but are now immune to it. They have lost interest in knowledge and will not continue to spread it.

Figure 1 – The sharing STP knowledge process and their dissemination

At the initial stage, there are only a small number of knowledge disseminators on the network, while other actors are potential knowledge recipients. The number of potential actors capable of spreading knowledge and immune to knowledge is zero. Over time, knowledge begins to spread in the following ways:

1. When knowledge disseminators transfer knowledge to potential knowledge recipients, recipients begin to accept it with a certain probability and become potential knowledge disseminators.

2. If potential knowledge disseminators are interested in knowledge, they will continue to disseminate it with some probability and become new knowledge disseminators.

3. Actors disseminating knowledge lose interest in knowledge with a certain probability and become immune to knowledge.

4. Non-disseminating knowledge again becomes knowledge recipients with a certain probability and accepts knowledge to which they are immune.

It is assumed that at a certain point in time during the knowledge dissemination in scientific cooperation networks, an actor can be in only one of the four states mentioned above. At a given point in time, it is proposed to determine the scientific cooperation subjects proportion that are in a certain knowledge dissemination state throughout the entire system, as follows:

– the knowledge potential recipients ratio to all actors in various STP knowledge dissemination states;

– the potential actors disseminating knowledge proportion to all actors in various STP knowledge dissemination states;

– the actors spreading knowledge proportion to all actors in different STP knowledge spreading states;

– the knowledge share unclaimed by all actors in various STP knowledge dissemination states.

When potential knowledge recipients interact with actors who disseminate knowledge through scientific collaboration, they can become potential actors who disseminate knowledge; potential STP knowledge dissemination actors become knowledge dissemination subjects; knowledge dissemination actors become knowledge-immune; and knowledge-immune actors generate feedback and become potential knowledge recipients.

The scientific collaboration network is a kind of complex networks with obvious scale-free properties. The distribution of their degrees (the nodes connections number) is consistent with the power distribution. The links between nodes are unevenly distributed, which means that only a minority of the nodes in the network have many links, while most of the nodes have few links. Actors of varying degrees at the network nodes play different roles in the STP knowledge dissemination. In accordance with the proposed approach to modeling the STP knowledge dissemination, the differential dynamics knowledge dissemination model in scientific cooperation of heterogeneity networks is formed by applying the mean field theory [9]. It is proposed to consider models for the differential dynamics knowledge dissemination in scientific cooperation networks, the nodal degrees of which are correlative and whose nodes degrees are not correlated.

It is proposed to adjust the parameters in order to obtain the most suitable model, namely, to achieve the maximum correspondence between the resulting values of the model and the actual indicators, which represent the share of actors disseminating knowledge in the scientific cooperation network. In accordance with the characteristics of theoretical and empirical data distributions, it is proposed to use the Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistics and the likelihood function for the assessment.

Maximum likelihood estimation is used to estimate the model parameters that best explain the data, independent measurements according to the noise model. The likelihood function is a statistical model parameters function that plays a key role in statistical inference. To make an optimal data estimate, it is proposed to use the negative logarithm of the likelihood function. The set of parameters for which the minimum value of the likelihood function is reached is the optimal set of parameters for the approximating model for the scientometric evaluation of STP results.

Scientometric assessment of STP results in each thematic area in the categories Web of Science (WoS) involves determining the level of representability (significance) of actors' publications in the global publications flow in this category, their relevance (degree of recognition by the world scientific community of the published results), as well as the publications scientific level in relation to the world. To obtain these characteristics, it is necessary to develop special methods and technologies for processing the corresponding bibliographic and bibliometric data, which allow taking into account the research process organization peculiarities and publication activity in various STP scientific areas. In addition, it is necessary to form criteria – tools for comparative analysis of the activity subjects scientific and technical potential development level with a different research thematic structure. The purpose of this analysis is to obtain data that allow ranking these subjects according to various STP potential characteristics. Based on the results of such a ranking, the range of those promising areas of domestic STP research that are most in demand by the world scientific community is determined.

Currently, to assess the contribution of the national STP complex to the development of world science, data on the articles citation level and the publications impact factor values in which they are published are mainly used, regardless of their thematic structure [10, 11]. This approach leads to a significant distortion of the real picture [12-14]. The fact is that even within the framework of one subject area, for example, chemistry, the average citation of publications of the world array over a five-year period in various thematic categories can differ several times. In addition, the average citations are noticeably higher in most subject categories in biology and medicine than in other areas of the natural sciences. Therefore, a direct comparison by this indicator of the national arrays of

publications is incorrect due to their significantly different thematic structure. It is obvious that the comparison of national pair of arrays that differ from each other by thematic or other characteristics, is incorrect without using a system of criteria that are invariant with respect to different directions. Unfortunately, not enough attention is currently paid to the development and use of such a system. The introduction of such a system of scientometric methods into research practice will significantly increase the reliability and comparability of the STP results obtained, as well as expand the range of problems to be solved. There are conceptual models for structuring a set of criteria for evaluating scientific areas, which are presented in the form of a multi-level information-logical structure of elements [15]. Moreover, the results obtained during the processing of expert-analytical information are presented in natural language without any transformations of qualitative data into quantitative ones using the methods of verbal analysis of decisions. Verbal decision analysis methods make it possible to solve the problems of supporting strategic decision-making in a more natural and constructive way and, in addition, to solve new types of scientific and technical planning problems.

Another important methodological problem, without the solution of which it is impossible to correctly determine the scale and scientific level of research, educational organizations, and other subjects of scientific activity STP is the problem of identifying these subjects.

It is necessary to develop a set of methods and tools that would allow for multi-stage iterative restructuring of the studied arrays. This will make it possible to highlight important structural data elements. After such a restructuring, it is possible to proceed to the identification of these data elements, which, in particular, will make it possible to determine the networks of scientific connections of scientists teams at various hierarchical organizational levels (organization, science sector, countries and organizations). Next, it is necessary to construct the distribution of the arrays of articles used in patent and scientific literature, on scientific topics, according to thematic areas of inventions, by organizations, according to the time lag between the scientific article publication moments and the patent publication moment for an invention, in which the fact of using this article is recorded. To compare the corresponding distributions of these arrays, a criteria set is needed that characterize various aspects of using the achievements of fundamental and applied science in patenting. It is also advisable to use the methodology for data envelopment analysis (DEA). DEA models allow building a multidimensional economic space, finding optimal ways of development in it, calculating the most important quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the behavior of STP actors, and simulating various situations [16]. The DEA methodology has a deep connection with theoretical economics, systems analysis, multi-criteria optimization. This approach will explore the scientific and technical potential of STP using direct methods. In addition, it is proposed to use original

methods for determining cross-sections based on metric spaces of multisets, which allow visualizing scientific and technical activities within the framework of STP in the multidimensional space of quantitative and qualitative indicators.

A significant methodological problem for assessing the relationship between research directions and the development of the technological sector of the economy is the identification of the thematic and organizational structure of STP publications that are used by patent authors, as well as by experts assessing the patentability of the application. The significance of the problem lies in the fact that the absence of such information does not make it possible to identify the factors influencing the activity of the practical use of the achievements of fundamental and applied science. The complexity of solving this problem from a methodological point of view is that it is necessary to combine fundamentally heterogeneous classification structures that are used in the processing of scientific and patent literature. A similar problem arises when comparing data on organizations whose employees are authors of scientific publications and authors of patented inventions. One of the methodological conclusions that can be drawn from the above consideration is that the procedures for restructuring and identifying initial data are an extremely important stage in the correct implementation of a scientometric study of the effectiveness of disseminating the results of modern scientific and technical programs, which, unfortunately, is not always implemented on practice. The use of the proposed scientometric approaches will make it possible to carry out a direct multidimensional comparison within the framework of the network paradigm of three different in nature information arrays corresponding to the STP results: an array of those publications that are presented in the WoS database; an array of inventions descriptions presented in the databases of patent services; an array of scientific articles cited by experts in patent search reports and / or by authors in the specified array of invention descriptions.

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